

MICROENCAPSULATED SOLVENT-BASED HEALING OF SHAPE MEMORY POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

Self-healing composites are materials that autonomously respond to damage in order to effect the restoration of a degraded property. The microcapsule-based self-healing approach embeds microencapsulated healing fluid(s) within a polymer matrix. These capsules rupture upon damage and initiate healing either by polymerization or mobilization of residual functionality. However, the finite fluid content contained within microcapsules limits the characteristic damage size that can be healed.

In the present research, we investigate the solvent-induced actuation and self-healing of shape memory polymers (SMP). The shape memory effect is activated by damage-induced release of microencapsulated solvent and serves to close and compress the fracture surfaces. The solvent then mechanically bonds the damaged area via polymer entanglement. This synergistic close-then-heal approach aims to enable healing of damage volumes larger than possible with non-SMP based systems.

Potential solvent compositions are screened using Hansen Solubility Parameters to identify multiple solvents suitable for activation of specific SMP materials. The effect of solvent on the SMP glass transition temperature was experimentally quantified by differential scanning calorimetry. Ex situ application of solvent is successfully shown to heal cuts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) are a type of smart polymer that can “remember” an initial shape, from which it can be elastically deformed and fixed into a secondary shape, to which it will return once exposed to a suitable stimulus [1]. The stimuli mobilize the polymer chains for molecular rearrangement of the matrix; possible stimuli include exposure to heat [1], light [2], or solvents [3].

Self-healing materials are materials capable of autonomous restoration of a degraded material property. These unique materials achieve this restoration via multiple healing routes, which can range from intrinsic re-bonding, to extrinsic routes, such as microcapsule-based and microvascular-based self-healing [4]. The characteristic damage volume that can be healed with microcapsule-based healing is typically restricted to 0.5 to 10 mm³. Greater damage volumes require transitioning to either a more complex approach (e.g., microvascular) or minimizing the damage volume to fit within this typical

size envelope. The synergistic use of SMPs and self-healing is a novel approach to enable the restoration of larger damages than could be achieved without the use of shape memory polymers.

2 SHAPE MEMORY POLYMERS

The reversible and predictable change in shape associated with shape memory polymers (SMPs) is labelled the shape memory effect. The shape memory effect is a process, during which the polymer mobility is dramatically increased and the configurational entropy of the polymer provides an entropic driving force for the restoration of the SMP's initial geometric state [5]. This initial state of the SMP body is formed during the polymerization process, in which the polymer chains propagate to form a crosslinked polymer networks; the crosslinking points determine the locked shape of the polymer body. When exposed to a stimulus that allows the polymer chains to become mobile (i.e., exceed the glass transition temperature), entropic forces drive the polymer body to return to its initial fabricated configuration in order to return polymer chains to their lowest energy state [2].

The shape memory effect is a generic effect that depends on the physical mechanism of polymer mobility, enabling the recovery driven by entropic forces. The triggering stimulus can be thermal, optical, electromagnetic, or solvent exposure. In this work the solvent exposure method was utilized to indirectly trigger the thermal shape memory effect. Rather than the typical route discussed in literature, in which an external heat source heats the polymer body to above its glass transition temperature, this method activates the shape memory effect by diffusing good solvents into the SMP polymer matrix. This solvent diffusion reduces the hydrogen bonding between neighboring polymer chains, thereby allowing the chains to move more freely and depressing the glass transition temperature of the SMP [6]. If solvent exposure is sufficient to lower T_g below the ambient temperature, the shape memory effect is triggered [2].

3 SELF-HEALING MATERIALS

3.1 Self-Healing Overview

Self-healing materials allow for the autonomous repair of material degradation mechanisms that compromise the functionality of the material system and are often difficult to detect and repair. The present work utilizes capsule-based self-healing in which a liquid solvent healing agent is sequestered within capsules embedded within the matrix. Damage to the matrix ruptures these capsules causing flow of the healing agents into the damaged region and the initiation of a re-connection between the damaged interfaces. The plasticizing effect from solvent exposure can allow molecular mobility to promote curing reactions [7].

3.2 Determination of Solvents Suitable for Self-Healing

Solvent-based self-healing benefits from strong interaction between the matrix and the encapsulated solvent. The prediction of solvents that are suitable for solvent-mediated healing can be estimated using the Hansen solubility parameters. The calculation of the Hansen solubility parameters are based on the cohesive energy of the molecule(s), which is a measure of the energy required to maintain the molecular bonds. The cohesive energy is the sum of the dispersion, polar and hydrogen bonding energy [8]. The difference between the dispersion, polar and hydrogen bonding energies of two chemicals can be used to predict whether or not the chemicals are mutually soluble, with chemicals having low differences in energies more likely to be soluble with one another.

4 DESIGN AND PRODUCTION OF SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER FILMS

4.1 Initial Shape Memory Recipe Selection and Film Production

A styrene co-polymer shape memory polymer (SMP) was synthesized according to the recipe from U.S. Patent No. 6,759,481. The baseline composition of the SMP was 90 wt% styrene monomer with a molecular weight of 280,000, 7 wt% vinyl neodecanoate, 1 wt% divinyl benzene, and 2 wt% benzoyl peroxide. All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The desired amount of styrene monomer

was pipetted into a 20 mL mixing cup, to which polystyrene pellets were added. Next, vinyl neodecanoate and divinyl benzene were added and the mixture homogenized using a dual asymmetric centrifugal mixer (model 150DCA, Flaktek) for 20 min at 2000 rpm. Lastly, the benzoyl peroxide powder is added and mixed in the centrifugal mixer for 20 min at 800 rpm.

The specimens were manufactured by pipetting 3 mL of the SMP solution onto a 150 mm square glass plate. A second square plate of identical size was placed on top of the SMP and approximately 0.1 psi of pressure applied, with care taken to not entrain air bubbles. Spacers between the plates made of strips of Kapton® tape were used as needed to dictate the film thickness. Prior to pipetting the SMP each glass plate was treated with a release agent (Rain-X™, SOPUS Products) so the SMP would not adhere to the plates after manufacturing. The specimens were cured at 75°C for 16 hrs.

4.2 Optimization of the Shape Memory Polymer Formulation

SMP specimens were initially manufactured with the entirety of the styrene component (90 wt% of the formulation) composed of styrene monomer. However, a large percentage of styrene monomer would evaporate before the SMP was fully cured. This evaporation made it difficult to obtain SMP specimens of useful size or consistency. To address this evaporation the formulation was modified to contain 30 wt% polystyrene as a replacement for one-third of the styrenic component. This modification to the formula results in a dramatic increase in the solution viscosity and a markedly lower evaporation rate. This modification enabled the reliable production of SMP film samples using the previously described method.

Early specimens also showed a yellow hue stemming in part from partial curing of the SMP prior to filmmaking. After this observation, all SMP specimens were stored at ~10°C to slow the polymerization kinetics. Batches older than 14 days were discarded, after the empirical observation of compromised production quality.

If the goal is to use the self-healing SMP material in a temperature range near room temperature, it is necessary to have a T_g suitably low so that solvent exposure can depress the T_g to ambient conditions. The T_g of the initial SMP formulation was determined by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and was determined to be 77°C. Solvent exposure in literature is capable of T_g depression ranging from 20-50°C, so composition changes to the formulation were explored to lower the baseline T_g of the SMP. A series of specimens were created from formulations in which the vinyl neodecanoate component was increased or decreased. These specimens were each characterized by DSC to determine the scope of decrease in the T_g . The effect of cure time was also tested to observe its effect on T_g . The glass transition temperatures determined by DSC are provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The SMP glass transition temperature for various cure times and weight fractions of vinyl neodecanoate. The yellow band indicates the cure temperature.

Each line on the chart in Figure 1 represents a SMP formulation with a different weight fraction of vinyl neodecanoate, and is plotted as a function of different cure times. The yellow band, which denotes the range of cure temperature, has a width of 5°C due to fluctuation in oven temperature. Two trends are observed, the first related to the effect of vinyl neodecanoate, and the second related to the cure cycle time.

The first trend is the effect of vinyl neodecanoate weight fraction on the glass transition temperature. While there is statistical scatter and overlap between neighboring curves, a relationship is discernible in which the SMP T_g is lowered by an increase in the weight fraction of vinyl neodecanoate. Specimens that contain a weight percent of greater than or equal to 9 wt% vinyl neodecanoate exhibit a plateau T_g value approximately 3-5°C lower than formulations containing less than 9 wt% vinyl neodecanoate. This effect is more pronounced prior to the plateau region, where the higher (9-13 wt%) vinyl neodecanoate weight fraction can reduce the T_g by 20°C relative to the low (e.g., 5 wt%) vinyl neodecanoate fractions.

The second trend relates the T_g to the cure cycle time. The values of T_g converge after 16 hours of cure time, indicating that prior to 16 hours specimens are not fully polymerized. This trend is supported by data from DSC tests involving multiple thermal cycles; specimens that were cured for less than 16 hours exhibited an increase in T_g between the first two cycles due to additional curing while being cycled from 0°C to 100°C in the DSC. Specimens that had been cured for greater than 16 hours did not exhibit this behavior. Hence, a minimum cure cycle time of 16 hours is recommended.

5 SOLVENT SCREENING AND SELECTION

The screening of solvents for glass transition temperature depression and self-healing potential consisted of solvent interaction calculations, human toxicity screening, and miscibility with water. An initial list of possible solvents was identified based on their calculated solubility parameters. These parameters are obtained from the Hansen Solubility Parameters in Practice (HSPiP) software package (version v4.0.x 2013). The SMP matrix was approximated by the software database values for

polystyrene. The software output a list of one hundred solvents that have the lowest calculated radial distance R from the styrene-based SMP in the polar-dispersion-hydrogen bonding parameter space. The initial list of solvents was down-selected based on a rapid, informal assessment of their overall human health hazards, with a preference for low toxicity substances. Finally, low miscibility with water is necessary to create an emulsion for the microencapsulation step. Hence, the miscibility of the least toxic substances with water were ascertained from chemical databases and chemicals preferentially selected that had low miscibility in water.

The solvent-polymer interactions of the best ten down-selected solvents, as well as water for purposes of a control solvent, were empirically measured by submerging SMP films into vials filled with solvent. Eleven 20 mL vials were filled with 10 mL of each solvent, while a twelfth vial was left empty to house a control specimen. Twelve SMP films were cut from a single SMP thin film and weighed. The films were heated in an oven to 80°C (i.e., above the T_g) and bent around a rod of ~7 mm diameter. The specimens were weighed a second time, then completely submerged within each solvent-containing vial. The vials were sealed and left for 24 hrs. Visual observations were made during the first hour and again at the 24 hour mark. After 24 hours, the specimens were removed with tweezers, any excess moisture was removed by drying with a Kimwipe wipe, and then weighed. The results are provided in Table 1.

Solvent	Mass Increase (%)	Time to Actuate
Ethyl Phenylacetate	370	15 min
Xylenes	345	5 min
Phenyl Acetate	328	10 min
Limonene Oil	165	5 hrs
Ethyl Acetate	158	5 min
Acetone	46.1	1 min
Methyl Oleate	42.2	4 hrs
Water	3.35	Did not uncurl
Dimethylsulfoxide	~ 0.00	Did not uncurl
Glycerol	~ 0.00	Did not uncurl
Triacetate		
Triacetin	~ 0.00	Did not uncurl
Air (Control)	~ 0.00	Did not uncurl

Table 1: Mass increase from solvent absorption test.

Solvent testing showed that ethyl phenylacetate (EPA) and xylenes induced the greatest mass gain in the polymer films with minimal time to activation of the shape memory effect. Therefore, subsequent encapsulation efforts focused on these solvents.

6 PRODUCTION OF MICROCAPSULES

Microcapsules are created using a procedure based upon the method described by Brown *et al.* and Blaiszik *et al.* [4,9-11]. A flowchart depicting the modified synthesis method can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Schematic of the steps to microencapsulated method, based on techniques from Brown *et al.* and Blaiszik *et al.* [4,9-11].

After the four hour polymerization of the urea-formaldehyde capsule shell, the emulsion was cooled in a cold water or ice bath and then vacuum filtered through filter paper that had a pore size of 5-10 μm . Once filtered, the capsules were left to dry at ambient temperature under atmospheric pressure with no desiccant for 24 to 48 hours prior to testing.

Using this procedure both ethyl phenylacetate (EPA) and xylenes were successfully encapsulated in capsules having an average diameter of 60 μm . These capsules were subsequently passed through a sieve to eliminate any capsules larger than 50 μm . The successful encapsulation of both EPA and xylenes liquids were confirmed through the use of TGA mass loss and FTIR analysis.

7 EX-SITU TESTING OF HEALING EFFICIENCY

Tests of the *ex situ* healing efficiency of the SMP material were performed with manual injection with the healing solvent(s). Dog bone-shaped specimens were created by punching samples out of the film using an ASTM D638 die. The dog bone specimens had a neck width of 3.175 mm and a neck length of 12.7 mm. The specimens were tested in an Instron 4464 machine with a 100 N load cell. The specimens were taped at either end to minimize tearing or cracking when clamped with pneumatic grips, and were loaded at a rate of 0.05 mm/min.

An accelerator (potassium oleate) was added to the SMP to reduce cure time and to reduce outward diffusion of the encapsulated solvent from the capsules into the matrix during the specimen cure cycle. In order to quantify the change in material properties made by the addition of the potassium oleate, specimens of both the original and modified recipes were mechanically tested. The average elastic modulus of the oleate-containing specimens was 834 MPa compared to the average of the neat specimens, which was 931 MPa. The average max stress and failure strain of the oleate specimens were 39.9 MPa and 3.38%, respectively, compared to 26.1 MPa and 2.91% for the neat specimens.

Specimens that broke cleanly in a single location were *ex situ* healed via manual injection of liquid drops via a syringe nozzle into the damage region and tested again after a 24 hour healing cycle. The healing fluids consisted of EPA solutions with varying weight fraction of dissolved polystyrene. The

solution compositions included EPA with 0, 10, 20, and 30 wt% dissolved polystyrene. Use of the neat EPA (i.e., 0 wt% polystyrene) solvent resulted in specimens which excessively wrinkled and could not be tested a second time. The results of the *ex situ* healing testing are provided in Table 2.

Specimen	Polystyrene loading (wt%)	Initial stress (MPa)	Healed stress (MPa)	Healing efficiency (%)
B3-01	10	24.3	10.4	43
B4-01	10	14.9	17.5	118
B8-01	20	8.8	8.5	96
B9-01	20	24.9	8.8	35
B10-01	20	27.5	4.8	18
B5-01	30	21.0	12.2	58
B6-01	30	24.3	9.0	37
B7-01	30	19.1	11.6	61

Table 2: *Ex situ* healing efficiency for SMP that was cured with potassium oleate and healed with EPA solvent containing 10%, 20% and 30% dissolved polystyrene.

The healing efficiency is set to be the ratio of the healed strength over the initial or virgin strength. Specimens B4-01, B6-01, and B8-01 were specimens in which the healed specimen fractured at the location of initial tensile fracture. The other specimens fractured at new, alternate locations. An example of the latter result is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3: *Ex situ* healing of an SMP specimen demonstrates fracture occurring at a different fracture location than the original cut. The scale bar is 10 mm.

This phenomenon of fracture occurring at the non-original location means that the healed cut was sufficiently strong for approximately half the specimens to fracture at a different location. This result suggests good healing, which the healing efficiencies reported in Table 2 support. Specimen B4-01, for instance, demonstrated a healing efficiency that exceeds 100%. The average healing efficiency for the tensile strength of all specimens was 58%, indicating that a majority of the original fracture strength is recovered after solvent healing.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This research investigated the fusion of two classes of ‘smart materials’: self-healing materials and shape memory polymers. These concepts were combined to create a shape memory polymer film that can heal from mechanical damage to restore an average of 58% original material tensile strength. The solvent-induced shape memory effect was demonstrated at ambient conditions and the two solvents with the greatest affinity for the shape memory polymer were successfully encapsulated. Solvent-based self-healing was demonstrated using both *ex situ* methods. Future work will demonstrate the *in situ* healing of films with embedded microcapsules, thereby requiring no external intervention during damage.

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